

PHILOSOPHICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPT OF THINKING AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of ideals of military heroism in the thinking of young people, the socio-philosophical foundations of the formation of ideals of military heroism in the thinking of young people are studied. Also, the theoretical aspects of the formation of ideals of military heroism in the thinking of young people are analyzed.

Key words: thinking, patriotism, idealism, phenomenon, rational, heroism, military heroism, historical, military courage, pride, national, philosophical, patriotism, moral, education.

INTRODUCTION. The deepening of democratic reforms and the further development of civil society in the new Uzbekistan show how powerful the harmony of real opportunity and historical ideal is. The harmony of real possibility and historical ideal is clearly manifested in the destiny of every nation and state and is enriched with new innovations based on the requirements of the time. This requires combining historical ideals with reality and using them as an educational mechanism.

As a result of the restoration of historical values, the growing process of national identity awareness of peoples, important positive changes are taking place in the way of thinking. These changes taking place in our lives are absorbed into the hearts and minds of people, and they cultivate a sense of confidence in the future, a sense of freedom and liberty. The new development strategy paves the way for us to enjoy our rich cultural and spiritual heritage, the springs of spirituality created by our great ancestors. Inculcating the educational process based on such historical values in young people remains one of the priority tasks.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. In the spiritual heritage created by mankind, ideas about heroism are found in mythological, religious-didactic, epic works such as the Avesta, Tripitaka, Ramayana, Mahabharata, Iliad, Alpomish, divine books such as the Torah, Psalms, Bible, Qur'an, hadiths and it is found in the examples of our classical literature, in the works of many philosophers. Problems of the impact of scientific research on historical and moral ideals on youth education R.Michner, S.Kautz, J.Sitser, Fernand Grenand,

Frederic Starr, Eiji Mano, Magida Mahluf, Mark Bonnell, Yul Janssens, Masataka Takeshita, Shi Yunli, P. Petrov, S.I. Tyulyayev, S.P. Tolstov, K. Pirliyev, R.R. Safin, I.F. Kharlamov, B. Toychiyev, I. Inoyatov, M. Abilov, V. Kaloshin, O. Abdurasulov, A. Sa'diyev . .Komilov, U. Mansur, U. Mahkamov, S. Nishonova, N. Artikov, O. Musurmonova, K. Qilichevalar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. First of all, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concept of "thinking". In "Philosophy: an encyclopedic dictionary" the concept of "thinking" is defined as follows: "Thinking (Arab. - thinking, intellectual knowledge) - determines the common, important features of objects and events, internal, necessary connections between them, legal a rational stage of cognition that reflects connections" [7].

According to Doctor of Psychology, Professor E. Ghaziyev, "thinking is the highest form of human mental activity, mental intelligence, conscious movement. Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for the rational implementation of a wide range of human activities" [1].

According to the psychologist scientist E.Z.Usmonova, thinking is a process that is formed in the conditions of social life, and it first manifests itself in the form of broad subject (practical) activity, and then it becomes a form that takes the character of "mental" behavior [6].

Another scientist K. Shonazarov proposed the following set of definitions of the concept of "thinking": thinking means the conscious reflection of reality with its objective features, connections, and relationships that cannot be directly perceived by a person; thinking begins when a problem arises for which there is no ready solution. A person begins to think when there is a need to know something; thinking is the activity of the mind aimed at clearly, deeply, fully and directly summarizing and directly reflecting (knowing) reality; thinking is the process of summarizing and reflecting objects and events with their legal connections and relationships in the human brain; thinking is a process of direct and generalized reflection of reality in the process of analysis and synthesis, socially related to the search and discovery of new things; thinking is a cognitive process aimed at indirectly and generalized reflection of the individual; thinking is an active perception of objective reality; It is the formation, movement and development of knowledge in the form of concepts, considerations, opinions, conclusions, theories and theories [8].

According to another definition, thinking is a high form of human mental activity; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. Thought is

considered a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, as well as the main condition for the implementation of human activities. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and accurately than intuition, perception, and imagination. In the process of thinking, thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses, etc. are formed in a person, and they are expressed in the mind of a person in the form of concepts, judgments, conclusions. Through human thinking, it summarizes reality and indirectly (indirectly), understands the most important connections, relationships, and features between things and events. Therefore, a person has the ability to foresee the emergence, development and consequences of social events and events based on certain laws, regulations and rules.

Thinking has the following main features:

1) it perceives reality in an abstracted and generalized way. In contrast to emotional cognition, thinking allows us to focus on its general, important, recurring properties and relationships, abstracting from the insignificant, secondary (usually determined by the task of cognition) features of the object;

2) thinking indirectly reflects existence. In it, new knowledge is created by relying on existing knowledge, without directly referring to experience every time. Thinking is based on the relationship between objects and events;

3) thinking is the creative activity of a person. In it, the cognitive process involves the creation of highly idealized objects (for example, concepts such as an absolute solid body, ideal gas), and the construction of various formal systems. With their help, it is possible to foresee and predict objects and events;

4) thought is inextricably linked with language. Thought is an ideal phenomenon. It is realized only in language - material phenomenon (sound waves, graphic lines), b. it enters into a form that people can directly accept and feel and becomes a means of exchange of ideas between people. In other words, language is a form of direct realization of thought [7]. Summarizing the above definitions, it can be said that thinking is a high form of human mental activity, and it is a tool for knowing the world around, a condition for the emergence of rational practical human activity. The thinking process begins when a problem situation arises for which there is no ready solution. That is, a person begins to think when he needs to know something.

Philosophical, psychological and pedagogical literature distinguishes two types of thinking: rational and irrational. M. Tajiyev and B. Ziyamhammadov call the second of these types of thinking thinking with the help of muroqaba

(inner feelings). According to them, the first reflects the private side of the objective entity, while the second is related to the wave front [5].

Rational thinking is carried out on the left side of the brain and expresses the properties of things and events. In this case, a person perceives the specific aspects of things and events in parts and rationally connects them to each other. Thinking with the help of Murokaba is mainly carried out in the right hemisphere of the brain, which feels the wave of objective existence. Through such thinking, a person can imagine, give in to emotions, create intentions and creativity, have fun, read fiction, engage in science. With the help of this type of thinking, a person can feel the objective existence as a whole - a set, and feel the necessary connection between the parts that make up this whole [5].

The laws of thought are the necessary connections between thoughts in the process of discussion, the requirements necessary for the correct construction of the discussion. The laws of thinking include the clarity of thought, the consistency and systematicity of thought, the non-contradiction of the thinking process, and the use of true judgments in the process of thinking.

The process of developing the thinking of young people is related to the development of their intellectual activity. Intellectual skills include the development of memory; development of perception; the development of imagination; reflects the development of attention [9].

Intellect is a personality trait, the ability to clearly and deeply reflect objects and events of objective existence in our mind with their specific connections and laws.

Intelligence is seen in all mental processes, primarily in thinking and creative imagination. It is more often observed when solving a bright new problem independently.

There are several qualities of intelligence, due to the fact that it is developed at different levels in different people: the clarity of the mind - the simplicity and reliability of thoughts, the absence of some kind of thought. This is not only intellectual, but in some sense moral. For the intelligibility of the mind is usually to feel responsible not only for action, but also for thoughts; rationality of the mind is a strict continuity and systematicity in thinking; depth of mind or thoughtfulness - the ability to recognize uniqueness in objects and events; breadth of mind - the ability to think taking into account all aspects of the issue; softness and flexibility of mind - absence of stereotypes, ability to change thinking; independence and originality. It is not a mere softness of mind, but innovation is a creative feature of mental activity; the criticality of the mind

is the absence of unexamined, simply received judgments, the existence of a deeply studied, analyzed, serious attitude to denials. All these individual characteristics of the human mind appear in the process of work, it is formed and developed [3].

Philosophy: in the encyclopedic dictionary, the concept of "ideal" is derived from the French "ideal" and the Latin "idealus", meaning "image", "criterion", "perfection". It is written as a term that expresses the highest goal of dreams and aspirations [7]. It is also noted in another foreign source that the concept of "ideal" means "idea" in Greek, i.e. "model", "norm" [4]. In our opinion, the ideal is an ideal image, has a normative character, and is important in determining the character and method of behavior of certain people or social groups. However, although there was a concept of "ideal" in the past, there was no name for the term of reality that represented it. Instead, various words and expressions were used and were called "realism" and "vitality". Ideal is an important philosophical category of social importance. Because of this, the social ideal is interpreted in close connection with the concept of "reality". Therefore, the term "social ideal" represents a set of knowledge aimed at knowing, understanding, and goodness of all aspects of social existence, and secondly, the desire for them. Therefore, dissatisfaction with the existing reality can be considered as an expression of the desire to improve the life of society and the state. And in the existing socio-political system and relations, the buds of the social ideal are formed.

Referring to the role of the ideal in the history of socio-philosophical thinking and various approaches, analyzes and interpretations in this regard, to see that this problem has been researched in the form of social-political, moral-aesthetic ideals in the activities of foreign and Uzbek scientists since the 60s of the 20th century. possible In particular, Russian scientists E. Ilyenkov "ideal - the highest value: the best ending of this or that event; A.N. Yassenko defines the ideal as the goal of the goal, connecting it with the social activity of a person [10].

CONCLUSION. Everyone strives for an ideal, compares his life to it, imitates it. It is the highest moral requirement in human life, the fulfillment of which brings the person to perfection. Of course, it cannot be fully achieved in life, but a person learns this perfection as an example and achieves relative life perfection in the process of living in pursuit of the ideal.

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